
ISSUES AND CHALLENGES AHEAD ACADEMIC LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

In this research article, there is a deep and valuable explanation about the various problems before Librarian, such as purchasing of reading material, library staff, library building and library space, library software low fund, of library, readers passiveness etc.

Introduction:

There are lot of problems and difficulties occurs, when any one do the work of any kind of institution which is related to the public. The institution which is related to the people has to face such kind of problems more than any other institution library is one of such institution related to societies. Dr. S.R. Rangnathan, the founder father of Library Information-Science, has said that the nature and scope of library-science is continuously changing and progressing. Changes, such as reading material, technology, new methods of exchange of books or providing facilities to readers. The library has changed and developed rapidly. Also the new issues and challenger are emerging. The librarian has to face the challenges and difficulties frequently. He tackles the various problems daily. Finally all blames have to face the librarian only. But other factors are also responsible for the problems before library.

The following difficulties or problems have to face librarian.

The Problems Relating to Reading Material:

1) Textbooks:

Textbooks are essential for academic libraries. The purchasing of textbook for Art, Commerce and Science streams is compulsory for library. Junior and Senior College students need various kind of books to fulfil the students demand, large quantity of textbooks have to maintain in library due to lack of funds these purchasing becomes impossible

2) References Books:

Various kind of reference book are essential for college library. Text book can be understood with the help of reference book. For purchasing of these references books the sufficient fund must be provided.

Lack of fund is the prominent difficulty in references books purchasing. The Government, the U.G.C. the administration should provide sufficient fund to libraries

3) Increasing Demand of Periodicals and their Costly Subscription:

Subject related periodicals must be kept in library to updating knowledge. But the prices are increasing rapidly. So,

maintaining periodicals is a challenging task. Timely publication of periodicals is a problem also. After dispatching from publisher periodical can't reach in time to the library.

4) E-Books, E- Journals Issues:

UGC suggested the professor and students should use E-Books, E-Journals, INFLIBNET has provided E-Books and E-Journals in Rs 5800 only. But students and college teaching staff ignore these facilities. Their response is so poor. This is one of the problems.

Issues Relating to Library Staff:

There are insufficient staffs working in libraries today. Number of staff members necessary for daily work. Because of this problem following difficulties arises

- 1) Untrained staff working improperly.
- 2) Various posts are empty, did not appoint proper candidate.
- 3) Other works, then library works have to do library staff.
- 4) Staff does not work effectively and sincerely.
- 5) Lack of training facilities for library staff.
- 6) Modern technology, Computer handling, Communication methods, there things are not be seen in library staff.
- 7) Government do not approved the essential staff for library.
- 8) So, this insufficient and untrained staff cannot fulfill the demands of students.

Issues Related to Fund Availability:

In recent years, there is a sharp decrease of fund allocation to libraries. The purchasing of necessary books, periodicals, textbooks is becoming difficult day by day

Provided fund not sufficient for following things.

- 1) Purchasing of furniture
- 2) Important but costly reference books
- 3) Computers, Xerox Machine, Printer cannot be purchased due to low availability of funds
- 4) Important Technology like RFID has to be ignored due to lack of funds
- 5) Valuable E-resources can't be provided by the librarian
- 6) The damaged books can not send for book-binding due to lack of fund

Need of Big Space for Library:

Today a library is a very important institute. It needs big pleasant space. The building of library should be big. Because the number of books, periodicals, newspapers, references books increasing rapidly. For these reading materials a big building needed for library

Also, readers are increasing so big reading room (hall) should be there.

Passiveness of Readers:

The present society ignoring knowledge. Readers not coming to read newspaper. Acceptance of new ideas, knowledge is ignored. Only exam related books are read. E-Books, E-Journals, reference books are ignored by readers. This is the major problem of today.

Problems of Software:

In every library, software frequently use. Software is the working of library. But some problems are seen there.

- 1) Unavailability of upgrade computers for new software.
- 2) Lack of trained staff for use of new software.
- 3) No supply of electricity. The problem of load shedding arises.

- 4) Fluctuation of electricity damages computers. So the working is badly affected.
- 5) Few software need internet, without internet they cannot work.
- 6) After some months or years, the barcode cannot be read by machine.
- 7) Sometime data can be deleted on a click. This valuable data very hard to regain.
- 8) Continue training is essential for changes in software, but the proper training is unavailable.
- 9) Technical problems in software cannot repaired in short time.

Other Difficulties the Librarian has to Face:

- 1) Some students damage the books, do not handle properly loose the books.
- 2) Many important E-resources need to be done but, lack of fund and untrained staff are main obstacles, in this process.
- 3) Periodicals do not send in time. There is always a delay.
- 4) Increasing prices of newspapers, periodicals etc. Put pressure on short funds.
- 5) The librarian has to perform other works also, such as invigilation in exam period, work as a cap-officer, other administrative works, etc. This is also a big problem.
- 6) No funds are there for book-binding.

- 7) Appointment of library staff not done.

Conclusion:

The librarian has to face such vast obstacles during his day to day duty. But, administration can solve these problems if they want. Today, librarian is working under tremendous pressure of these problems, solving problems on his level.

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